

HMRC's Anti-Fraud Intervention on Child Benefit — Written Evidence

House of Commons Public Accounts Committee

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The Central Problem

Between August and October 2025, HMRC suspended Child Benefit payments for approximately 23,794 families using Home Office flight data to identify claimants suspected of non-residence, as part of an initiative designed to save £350 million over five years (Cabinet Office et al., 2025; National Audit Office, 2026). The exchequer secretary subsequently confirmed to Parliament that 14,994 of those customers (63 per cent) were confirmed eligible, only 1,019 (4.3 per cent) were determined to have been incorrectly receiving Child Benefit, and 7,781 enquiries remained open (Tomlinson, 2025). As of March 2026, approximately 60 per cent of suspended cases had been reinstated (National Audit Office, 2026).

Internal HMRC risk documentation assessed the risk of erroneous flagging as "remote" and "tolerable" before full deployment and rated the severity of potential harm as "minimal" (Butterly, 2026b). Yet the pilot itself showed that travel data was wrong in approximately 46 per cent of cases, and more than a third of those investigated for suspected fraud were ultimately found to be legitimate claimants (Butterly, 2026b; O'Carroll, 2025b). The National Audit Office is investigating the intervention's strategy, governance, design, implementation, and management, with findings expected in Summer 2026 (National Audit Office, 2026).

This submission argues that the intervention's failures are attributable to three interconnected governance failures: governance filtering, a deployment accountability gap, and

accountability displacement. Each is structurally predictable, preventable by design, and will recur in future data-driven interventions unless addressed as design requirements rather than post-hoc lessons.

1. Governance Filtering: How a 46 Per Cent Error Rate Became "Remote Risk"

The pilot scheme produced an error rate of approximately 46 per cent in the Home Office travel data (Butterly, 2026b). This figure was available to HMRC officials before the decision to deploy the intervention to nearly 24,000 families. Yet the Data Protection Impact Assessment recorded the risk of erroneous flagging as "remote" and the severity of consequential harm as "minimal" (Butterly, 2026b).

This gap between operational evidence and governance assessment is not a product of individual negligence. It reflects a structural dynamic that organisational theorists have documented extensively: under delivery pressure, repeated exposure to anomalous data progressively normalises deviation from safety standards (Vaughan, 1996), and as information moves up hierarchical structures, operational urgency is converted into compliance language and assessments calibrated to avoid blame rather than capture risk (Hood, 2011; Shabad, 2026). Governance documents come to reflect a sanitised version of operational reality shaped by the incentives of the teams producing it.

Governance filtering means that decision-makers at the approval stage receive a risk picture already shaped by institutional pressures to proceed. The teams involved faced stronger incentives to proceed — fraud reduction targets, cost-saving mandates, delivery pressure — than to halt, and the DPIA consultation was conducted to inform stakeholders rather than to solicit challenge. As Mariano delli Santi (Open Rights Group) observed, this inverts the purpose of consultation, which "is not to inform but to gather feedback and identify potential risks" (Butterly, 2026b). Independent legal experts have since questioned whether the process met the proportionality standard required under UK data protection law (O'Carroll, 2025a).

The consequence is that the formal governance artefact — the DPIA — did not function as an accountability mechanism. It functioned as a procedural checkpoint that the intervention passed without meaningful scrutiny of the underlying data quality evidence. That this

dynamic persisted into the rollout phase is confirmed by a subsequent internal HMRC report, which described the intervention as it was generating thousands of wrongful suspensions as follows: "The data share aspects of the exercise remain consistent with what was expected" (Butterly, 2026a).

This pattern has precedent. The NAO's investigation into the WannaCry ransomware attack found that cybersecurity alerts, governance structures and reporting chains formally existed, yet 80 NHS trusts were disrupted by an attack exploiting a publicly known vulnerability for which a patch had been available for two months (National Audit Office, 2018). Formal compliance did not produce substantive scrutiny.

The data quality limitation that governance filtering concealed was not a post-hoc discovery. The permanent secretary's letter to the Treasury Select Committee confirms: "It was understood from the outset and made clear by the Home Office that this data could not be used in isolation for interpreting a customer's residency status" (Marks, 2025). Governance filtering converted this known constraint into a risk-management caveat rather than a threshold condition for deployment.

2. The Deployment Accountability Gap: A Pilot Without a Pass/Fail Threshold

A pilot scheme serves two distinct functions. The first is learning: understanding how a new approach performs in practice. The second is gating: establishing whether the intervention is ready to scale. The first function is inherently retrospective. The second requires a pre-defined threshold — a standard against which pilot results are measured before a scale-up decision is authorised.

HMRC's pilot appears to have served the first function but not the second. There is no evidence in the public record of a pre-defined acceptable error rate established before the pilot commenced, against which the approximately 46 per cent figure would automatically require a halt or ministerial re-approval before scaling. Without such a threshold, a 46 per cent error rate can be absorbed into the governance narrative as a "learning" rather than a "failure" — which is precisely what the subsequent DPIA language suggests (Butterly, 2026b).

This is a deployment accountability gap: the absence of a named individual or governance body with explicit authority to determine that a pilot has not passed, and explicit responsibility to prevent scaling until the standard is met. HM Treasury's own Test and Learn guidance sets two explicit requirements for any government pilot moving to full deployment. First, teams must "agree decision criteria before testing begins" (HM Treasury, 2026). No such criteria were established for this intervention: there was no documented error rate at which the pilot would be deemed to have failed. Second, an intervention should "only move from the Test phase into the Grow phase once the intervention has reached a steady state — where its design, delivery and core processes are stable and operating as intended" (HM Treasury, 2026). The expansion demonstrably did not meet this standard: the permanent secretary confirmed that the PAYE check — a core operational safeguard present throughout the pilot — was removed for the expansion (Marks, 2025), and the exchequer secretary confirmed to Parliament that HMRC "put in place an expedited process for customers that varied from the way it applied checks in the pilot" (Tomlinson, 2025). An expansion that removes a core safeguard and introduces a materially different process is not a steady-state transition. Both requirements of HM Treasury's own guidance were absent; neither was documented as having been waived.

Consequently, no named individual was accountable for the scale-up decision: no official signed off that the pilot had passed, because no standard of passing had been defined. The same written answer states that "the information from the pilot remains HMRC's best assessment of the effectiveness of the activity" (Tomlinson, 2025) — leaving the pilot that was not used to gate scaling as HMRC's only validated baseline.

This Committee's 2023 report on tackling fraud and corruption against government recommended that Initial Fraud Impact Assessments (IFIA) be embedded in HM Treasury's formal spending approval processes, and that they inform Accounting Officer Assessments before new schemes proceed (Committee of Public Accounts, 2023). This submission invites the Committee to establish whether an IFIA was conducted for this intervention and, if so, whether its findings were reflected in the documented decision to proceed to full rollout.

3. Accountability Displacement: Who Answers When the Algorithm Is Wrong?

By late November 2025, 14,994 families confirmed as legitimate UK-resident claimants had had Child Benefit suspended (Tomlinson, 2025): payments stopped on the basis of flights never boarded and countries never visited, in each case because the data was wrong, not the claimant (Butterly, 2025; O'Carroll, 2025d). The Information Commissioner's Office reminded HMRC that public-body data sharing must be "necessary, proportionate" and rely on data that is "accurate and fit for purpose" (O'Carroll, 2025a).

In each case, the decision to suspend was taken by an automated process acting on data that was factually wrong. The consequences — financial disruption, stress, stigmatisation — were experienced by real individuals. But no individual at HMRC made a decision about these specific families. The algorithm acted; the data was wrong; and the consequences were absorbed by claimants who had to navigate an appeals process to prove their continued residence.

This is accountability displacement: when automated systems make decisions, the chain of human responsibility for individual outcomes breaks. HMRC officials can truthfully say that no officer decided to suspend a particular family's payments — the data matching flagged them, the system suspended them, and they could appeal. This is formally accurate and substantively inadequate. The chair of the Treasury Select Committee asked precisely the right governance question in November 2025: "what level of seniority was involved in the signoff of the anti-fraud initiative?" (O'Carroll, 2025c). The absence of a clear public answer is itself informative: a system that can disrupt nearly 15,000 families' finances without a named human being responsible is itself a governance choice.

HMRC's account to the Treasury Select Committee illustrates how this architecture was characterised internally: "no automated decisions are taken by HMRC to end entitlement to Child Benefit" (Marks, 2025). This formulation is technically accurate — automated processes suspended rather than terminated entitlement — but it precisely describes the displacement this submission identifies. A claimant who must navigate a compliance enquiry to restore income they are lawfully entitled to has experienced a consequential decision. That

no named official made that specific decision about that specific family is not a vindication of the system's accountability structure; it is an account of its design.

Accountability displacement is not inevitable. It is a consequence of specific design choices: no manual review stage before suspension; removal of the PAYE cross-check to "streamline" the process, confirmed by the permanent secretary (Butterly, 2026b; Marks, 2025); no prior contact with the claimant. Each reduced human involvement in individual outcomes and therefore the scope for human accountability for them.

Each was subsequently reversed: HMRC reinstated the PAYE check, introduced prior notification, and excluded Northern Ireland cases from future enquiries (Marks, 2025). These corrections validate rather than rebut the analysis here. They are precisely the safeguards that architectural accountability would have required before deployment — adopted retrospectively, at the cost of 14,994 wrongful suspensions.

4. Lessons for Future Design: Architectural Accountability

The preceding failures point to the need for architectural accountability: an explicit framework, established before deployment, that specifies who answers when a data-driven intervention produces wrong outcomes. This requires four components.

Decision rights mapping — explicit specification of which decisions can be automated and which require human review before execution. The suspension of a claimant's benefit payments without prior contact is a significant decision affecting a family's income. Governance design should require explicit determination of whether this decision can be taken without human review, and if so, under what conditions.

Escalation triggers — pre-defined thresholds that automatically require human review before an automated decision is enacted or before a programme scales. A pilot error rate of approximately 46 per cent should be a defined trigger for halt and ministerial re-approval, not a data point to be absorbed into a DPIA narrative (Butterly, 2026b). Escalation triggers must name the individual accountable for the decision at that trigger point.

Assumption registers — explicit documentation of the conditions that must hold for the intervention to be reliable, with monitoring for when those conditions fail. HMRC used Home Office data that the Home Office itself characterised as indicative: a subject access request revealed the Home Office's own statement that "any travel history provided should be interpreted as an intention to travel and not as proof of travel" (O'Carroll, 2025a). That caveat did not appear in the DPIA's assessment of fitness for purpose. An assumption register would have made this visible and required ongoing monitoring — for example, audits of data accuracy against PAYE records — rather than leaving errors to surface through appeals (National Audit Office, 2025).

Upstream data audits — independent assessment of the data used to identify potential fraud before it is used at scale. The Home Office flight data contained unconfirmed bookings, incomplete border records and known identity confusions (Butterly, 2025). One error typology was constitutional rather than technical: because the 1998 Belfast Agreement removed passport controls on the Irish land border, the Home Office structurally cannot record return journeys made via Dublin Airport. Northern Irish families who routinely fly out of Belfast and return via Dublin were therefore systematically recorded as having left the UK without returning (Butterly & O'Carroll, 2025). This error was predictable from the constitutional settlement; a pre-deployment audit against known cross-border travel patterns would have identified it before a single family was wrongly suspended.

Recommendations

- 1. Pre-defined acceptance criteria for pilot-to-scale transitions.** Any data-matching intervention affecting benefit payments should require a documented, pre-approved false positive rate threshold before the pilot commences; if exceeded, a named Senior Responsible Owner must provide documented justification with ministerial sign-off before scaling. Any material divergence between the pilot and the scaled implementation — such as removing a safeguard that operated throughout the pilot — should require the same level of authorisation. Both requirements reflect HM Treasury's own Test and Learn guidance: teams must "agree decision criteria before testing begins" and should "only move from the Test phase into the Grow phase once the intervention has reached a steady state" (HM Treasury, 2026).

2. **Architectural accountability frameworks for automated benefit decisions.** Before deploying any automated intervention affecting payments at scale, HMRC should be required to publish a framework specifying: which decisions are automated and which require human review; who is accountable for decisions at defined trigger thresholds; what assumptions underlie the data used; and how upstream data quality will be audited on an ongoing basis.
3. **Named accountability for aggregate outcomes.** When automated processes produce systematic errors affecting thousands of claimants, a named individual should be accountable for the architectural design decisions — deploying without a pass/fail threshold, removing the PAYE check, suspending without prior notification — not for each individual automated decision, which by design no human made. Holding frontline operators responsible would recreate what Elish (2019) terms the "moral crumple zone". Cabinet Office guidance on Senior Responsible Owners should be extended to data-driven enforcement interventions, so these choices remain traceable to named human judgment.

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Declarations

AI use: During the preparation of this submission, the author used Claude (Anthropic) to improve readability and language quality as a non-native English speaker. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content and takes full responsibility for the content of this submission.

Competing interests: The author declares no financial interest in the outcome of this inquiry. The author is the sole author of the academic work cited herein.